

Association of Socio-demographic and Lifestyle Factors with Metabolic Syndrome: A Cross-Sectional Study in Urban Setting

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Abstract

Background: Bangladesh, undergoing an epidemiological transition highlighted by the Global Burden of Disease study, faces a considerable Non-Communicable Diseases (NCDs) burden, with Metabolic Syndrome (MetS) being a prominent contributor, accounting for 70% of total mortality in 2019. Urban environments are dynamic settings where lifestyle factors intertwine with socio-demographic variables, influencing health outcomes. This study aimed to ascertain the prevalence of MetS and explore associated socio-demographic and lifestyle factors in an urban setting of Bangladesh.

Methods: A cross-sectional study was conducted from July 2010 to June 2011 among residents of three government residential facilities in the Mirpur area of Dhaka city. A total of 347 participants of both sexes, aged between 30 and 74 years were selected by purposive sampling method. Information on socio-demographic, lifestyle, and medical history were collected by a pre-tested questionnaire. Additionally, anthropometric measurements were taken and blood pressure was measured. Fasting blood samples were collected to assess lipid profile and blood sugar from the extracted serum and plasma. MetS was defined according to the National Cholesterol Education Program's Adult Treatment Panel III (ATP III) and International Diabetes Federation (IDF) criteria.

Results: The overall prevalence of MetS was 43.2% (95% CI: 38.1-48.5) based on ATP III criteria and 42.9% (95% CI: 37.8-48.2) based on IDF criteria. Bivariate analysis demonstrated significant associations between MetS, as defined by IDF criteria, and age groups ($p < 0.007$), gender ($p < 0.001$), employment status ($p < 0.001$), and BMI ($p < 0.001$). Similarly, when defined by ATP III criteria, MetS had significant associations with employment ($p < 0.005$) and BMI ($p < 0.001$). Multivariate logistic regression indicated higher odds of MetS, defined by IDF criteria, among the 40-49 age group (AOR=2.5, 95% CI: 1.4-4.4), while for MetS defined by ATP III criteria, the 50-59 age group had higher odds (AOR=2.1, 95% CI: 1.0-4.1). MetS, defined by both criteria, had lower odds among the employed group (AOR=0.4, 95% CI: 0.2-0.9). Additionally, obesity exhibited the highest odds, particularly for MetS defined by IDF criteria (AOR=6.2, 95% CI: 2.5-15.1).

Conclusions: These findings lay the foundation for a comprehensive exploration of the intricate interplay between demographic characteristics, lifestyle factors, and metabolic syndrome in an urban setting.

Keywords: Metabolic syndrome, socio-demographic factors, lifestyle factors, urban, Bangladesh

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Introduction

Over the past three decades, global disease patterns have undergone notable transformations, marked by a surge in the prevalence of Non-Communicable Diseases (NCDs).¹ Metabolic Syndrome (MetS), characterized by abdominal obesity, insulin resistance, hypertension, and hyperlipidemia, has experienced a worldwide increase, impacting approximately 20-25% of the global popula-

tion.² Particularly in South Asian countries such as India, Nepal, Pakistan, Sri Lanka, and Bangladesh, escalating rates of obesity, sedentary lifestyles, and dietary changes have contributed to a high MetS prevalence ranging from 20.7% to 35.5%.³ Bangladesh, undergoing an epidemiological transition highlighted by the Global Burden of Disease study, faces a considerable NCDs burden, with MetS being a prominent contributor, accounting for 70% of total mortality in 2019.^{4,5} The risk conferred by MetS extends beyond cardiovascular diseases and type 2 diabetes, encompassing an elevated risk of all-cause mortality.⁶

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In 2001, the National Cholesterol Education Program Adult Treatment Panel III (NCEP) laid the foundation for defining MetS, a framework later refined in 2005 by the American Heart Association/National Heart, Lung, and Blood Institute (Modified NCEP) and the International Diabetes Federation (IDF).⁶⁻⁸ Despite these efforts, discrepancies in prevalence estimates persist due to the multitude of definitions, prompting the Joint Interim Statement (JIS) to seek harmonization.⁹ Individuals with MetS face a five-fold increased risk of type 2 diabetes and a two-fold risk of cardiovascular diseases over the next 5 to 10 years, along with an elevated risk of stroke, myocardial infarction, and mortality.¹⁰ Identifying and assessing those at risk of MetS becomes crucial for informing preventive actions.¹¹

Urban environments are dynamic settings where lifestyle factors intertwine with socio-demographic variables, influencing health outcomes.¹² In Dhaka, where rapid urbanization is transforming traditional patterns of living, investigating the nexus between these factors and MetS becomes pivotal. The diverse socio-demographic landscape of Dhaka, encompassing variations in age, gender, education, occupation, and marital status, offers a unique opportunity to discern patterns and identify vulnerable subpopulations. In this regard our study focuses on the urban Mirpur population, aiming to ascertain the prevalence of metabolic syndrome based on both ATP III and IDF criteria, and explore associated socio-demographic and lifestyle factors. The findings are anticipated to enrich the existing body of knowledge, informing evidence-based public health initiatives aimed at mitigating the impact of MetS in rapidly urbanizing contexts.

Methodology

Study design, setting and participants

This cross-sectional population-based study was conducted from July 2010 to June 2011 in three government colonies located in the Mirpur area of Dhaka city. These colonies serve as residential areas for numerous families of government service holders from various districts. A total of 347 participants, encompassing both sexes and aged between 30 and 74 years, were recruited for the study by purposive sampling. Participants were residents of the flats who adhered to the study instructions, including a requirement for a 12-hour overnight fasting period.

Exclusions from the study comprised pregnant women and individuals with known cardiovascular disease (CVD) cases. Field assistants approached potential participants and obtained informed consent. Interviews and measurements were conducted at the household level. Each participant received a referral card and was requested to visit the Bangladesh Institute of Health Sciences (BIHS) hospital for blood sample collection on a pre-arranged date after a 12-hour overnight fast. Emphasis was placed on the importance of adhering to the fasting state for a minimum of 12 hours before the blood sample collection during the data

collection phase. The methodology also described in another published article from this dataset.¹³

This approach ensured standardized conditions for assessing metabolic parameters and contributed to the overall reliability and validity of the study results.

Interview

Participants underwent face-to-face interviews, during which they provided general information and lifestyle data through a pre-tested questionnaire. The entire interview process, which included obtaining informed consent, blood pressure measurement, and collecting general baseline data, lasted a maximum of 30 to 40 minutes. During the interview, participants were queried about their smoking status and alcohol consumption. Additionally, participants were asked to provide information about their medical history, specifically regarding conditions such as diabetes and hypertension. The comprehensive nature of the interview allowed for a holistic understanding of both lifestyle factors and pre-existing health conditions, contributing to a more nuanced analysis of the data.

Anthropometric measurements

Weight, measured with a daily-calibrated digital weighing machine (TANITA LOT No. 890919), required participants to stand motionless with equal weight distribution on both legs and removal of shoes and excess clothing, with measurements recorded to the nearest 0.1 kg. Height was measured with a locally prepared wooden stadiometer to the nearest 0.1cm, ensuring participants stood in a specified posture with shoes off. Waist circumference was measured mid-way between the lowest rib margin and iliac crest, with participants standing erect, breathing normally, and measurements taken after expiration, recorded to the nearest centimeter. Hip circumference, measured at the level of the greatest protrusion of the gluteal muscles, involved participants standing with even weight distribution and legs slightly apart, with measurements also recorded to the nearest centimeter.

Blood pressure measurements

Blood pressure measurements were conducted with participants in a seated position, ensuring that the calf was positioned at the level of the heart. Following a 10-minute rest period, a second and third reading were taken. Systolic blood pressure (SBP) and diastolic blood pressure (DBP) were determined by noting Korotkoff sounds I (the first sound) and V (the disappearance of sound), respectively, in accordance with WHO-ISH guidelines, measured in millimeters of mercury (mmHg). The average of the second and third readings was calculated for blood pressure assessment.

Blood sample collection

On the pre-scheduled date and time at the laboratory of Bangladesh Institute of Health Sciences (BIHS), the participant's fasting state was confirmed, and 5cc of venous blood

was collected with aseptic precautions. After 20 minutes, the blood samples underwent centrifugation for 10 minutes at 6000 rpm to separate plasma and serum. The obtained plasma and serum were then preserved in a freezer at -27°C for future biochemical analysis. This meticulous process ensures the integrity of the biological samples and facilitates accurate biochemical assessments in subsequent analyses.

Laboratory Assays

The Biomedical Research Group (BMRG) at the Bangladesh Institute of Research and Rehabilitation in Diabetes, Endocrine, and Metabolic Disorders (BIRDEM) conducted the analysis of fasting, along with triglycerides and HDL cholesterol. For glucose measurements, the Glucose Oxidase (GOD-PAP) method (Randox Laboratories Ltd., UK), was employed. Serum triglyceride levels were estimated using an enzymatic colorimetric method (GOD-PAP) with reagents (Randox Laboratories, UK), and serum high-density lipoprotein (HDL-C) levels were measured using an enzymatic colorimetric method (cholesterol CHOD-PAP) (RANDOX Laboratories, UK). All biochemical estimations were performed on a Hitachi 704 autoanalyzer, ensuring standardized and precise results.

Data quality checking and processing

Following collection, the data underwent rigorous scrutiny for consistency and completeness. An initial check was performed on the day of collection to identify and rectify any errors, inconsistencies, or incompleteness. Subsequently, the data was entered into Microsoft Excel, categorized, and coded for accuracy and facilitate comprehensive analysis.

Outcome variable

Metabolic syndrome (NCEP ATP III criteria)^{6,14}

Diagnosing MetS, as per NCEP ATP III criteria, involved identifying abdominal obesity through increased waist circumference, elevated triglycerides, decreased HDL, high blood pressure, and elevated plasma glucose. In this context, an individual was considered to have MetS if they exhibited any three of the following conditions:

1. Blood Pressure (BP): Systolic ≥ 130 mmHg or diastolic ≥ 85 mmHg or currently taking antihypertensive medication.
2. Fasting Blood Glucose (FBG): ≥ 100 mg/dl or currently taking medication.
3. Serum Triglycerides: ≥ 150 mg/dl or currently taking medication.
4. HDL cholesterol: < 40 mg/dl (Male), < 50 mg/dl (Female) or currently taking medication.
5. Waist circumference: > 102 cm (Male), > 88 cm (Female).

Metabolic syndrome [IDF criteria]^{8,14}

According to the IDF definition, individuals were classified as having MetS if they exhibited central adiposity along with two or more additional factors. In this context, the criteria included a waist circumference of ≥ 90 cm (Male) or

≥ 80 cm (Female), in addition to any two of the following four conditions:

1. Blood Pressure (BP): Systolic ≥ 130 mmHg or diastolic ≥ 85 mmHg or currently taking antihypertensive medication.
2. Fasting Blood Glucose (FBG): ≥ 100 mg/dl or currently taking medication.
3. Serum Triglycerides: ≥ 150 mg/dl or currently taking medication.
4. HDL cholesterol: < 40 mg/dl (Male), < 50 mg/dl (Female) or currently taking medication.

Statistical methods

The study employed statistical methods to analyze the proportional distributions of metabolic syndrome based on both ATP III and IDF criteria across various socio-demographic and lifestyle characteristics. Chi-square tests were utilized for categorical variables, examining associations with age, gender, education, employment, marital status, smoking habits, chewing tobacco, dietary patterns, physical activity, and body mass index. To assess the strength of association, multivariate logistic regression analysis was conducted, reporting odds ratios (OR) while adjusting for potential confounders. Results were presented as proportions with 95% confidence intervals, and statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$. These rigorous analyses were performed using STATA 17, aiming to provide a comprehensive understanding of the intricate relationships between demographic and lifestyle factors influencing metabolic syndrome within the urban population.

Ethical consideration

Study obtained ethical clearance from the Institutional Review Board of Bangladesh Institute of Health Sciences (BIHS). Before the interview and blood sample collection each participant provided informed written consent. Additionally, prior to commencing household visits, permission was obtained from the local committee of each colony block.

Results

Distributions of metabolic syndrome (MetS) across various socio-demographic characteristics in the urban Mirpur population of Dhaka, using both ATP III and IDF criteria are shown in Table 1. The overall prevalence of MetS was 43.2% (95% CI: 38.1-48.5) based on ATP III criteria and 42.9% (95% CI: 37.8-48.2) based on IDF criteria. When examining age groups, no significant differences were observed overall ($p = 0.315$) under ATP III criteria. However, the 40-49 age group showed a notably higher proportion based on IDF criteria (43.6%, $p < 0.007$). Gender differences were statistically significant, with females exhibiting a significantly higher proportion compared to males under both criteria (ATP III: 65.3%, IDF: 73.2%, $p = 0.060$ and $p < 0.001$, respectively). Educational attainment did not show significant associations overall. In terms of occupation, a significant difference emerged ($p < 0.005$ and $p < 0.001$)

between the unemployed and employed groups. Specifically, the proportion of MetS was higher among the unemployed (ATP III: 61.3%, IDF: 67.1%) compared to the employed group. Marital status did not display significant associations with MetS. These findings underscore the socio-demographic variations in the prevalence of MetS in the Mirpur urban population, emphasizing the notable influence of gender and occupational status on the observed patterns.

Table 1: Proportional distribution of metabolic syndrome stratified by socio-demographic characteristics

Variables	n (%)	ATP III Criteria n (%)	p-value	IDF Criteria n (%)	p-value
Overall		43.2 (95% CI: 38.1-48.5)		42.9 (95% CI: 37.8-48.2)	
Age groups					
30-39	154 (44.4)	40.0	p=0.315	36.9	p<0.007
40-49	116 (33.4)	33.3		43.6	
50-59	62 (17.9)	21.3		16.1	
≥60	15 (4.3)	5.4		3.4	
Gender					
Male	140 (40.3)	34.7	p=0.060	26.8	p<0.001
Female	207 (59.7)	65.3		73.2	
Education					
Primary	47 (13.5)	16.7	p=0.287	18.1	p=0.079
SSC	136 (39.2)	39.3		38.9	
HSC & above	164 (47.3)	44.0		42.9	
Employment					
Unemployed	182 (52.4)	92 (61.3)	p<0.005	100 (67.1)	p<0.001
Employed	165 (47.5)	58 (38.7)		49 (32.9)	
Marital status					
Unmarried	25 (7.2)	10 (6.7)	p=0.735	10 (6.7)	p=0.758
Married	322 (92.8)	140 (93.3)		139 (93.3)	

n = Sample size, % = percentage, 95% CI = 95% confidence interval
p<0.05= Significance level obtained by Pearson chi-square test

Table 2 presents the proportional distribution of MetS stratified by lifestyle characteristics in the urban Mirpur population of Dhaka, assessed using both ATP III and IDF criteria. For smoking habits, no significant association was observed overall, but under IDF criteria, a significant difference emerged (p<0.02). Specifically, individuals who never smoked exhibited a higher proportion of MetS (85.9%). Chewing tobacco did not demonstrate overall significant association. Insufficient fruit and vegetable intake showed no significant association with metabolic syndrome. Physical activity levels did not exhibit an overall significant association; however, individuals with an inactive lifestyle demonstrated a slightly higher proportion of MetS under both criteria. Waist-hip ratio exhibited a significant association with MetS under IDF criteria (p<0.041), indicating a higher proportion in individuals with an elevated waist-hip ratio (79.9%). Body Mass Index (BMI) categories displayed significant associations under both ATP III and IDF criteria (p<0.001). Specifically, individuals classified as overweight or obese showed a significantly higher proportion of MetS (ATP III: 40.0%, IDF: 45.6%). These findings underscore the importance of smoking habits, BMI, and waist-hip ratio

in understanding the prevalence of MetS in the Mirpur urban population, emphasizing the need for lifestyle modifications in targeted public health interventions.

Table 2: Proportional distribution of metabolic syndrome stratified by life-style characteristics

Variables	n (%)	ATP III Criteria n (%)	p-value	IDF Criteria n (%)	p-value
Smoking					
Never	273 (78.7)	118 (78.7)	p=0.898	128 (85.9)	p<0.02
Current	64 (18.4)	27 (18.0)		18 (12.1)	
Past	10 (2.3)	5 (3.3)		3 (2.0)	
Chewing tobacco					
Never	304 (87.6)	126 (84.0)	p=0.075	127 (85.2)	p=0.244
Current/past	43 (12.4)	24 (16.0)		22 (14.8)	
Insufficient fruits and vegetable					
Yes	253 (72.9)	113 (75.3)	p=0.376	106 (71.1)	p=0.520
No	94 (27.1)	37 (24.7)		43 (28.9)	
Physical activity					
Inactive	152 (43.8)	66 (44.0)	p=0.949	62 (41.6)	p=0.475
Active	195 (56.2)	84 (56.0)		87 (58.4)	
BMI categories					
Normal/Under weight	192 (55.3)	67 (44.7)	p<0.001	55 (36.9)	p<0.001
Overweight	121 (34.9)	60 (40.0)		68 (45.6)	
Obese	34 (9.8)	23 (15.3)		26 (17.5)	

n = Sample size, % = percentage, 95% CI = 95% confidence interval
p<0.05= Significance level obtained by Pearson chi-square test

In the multivariate analysis (AOR) (Table 3), several key findings emerged. Notably, the age group of 40-49 exhibited a significantly higher odds ratio for MetS under IDF criteria, with adjusted odds ratios (AOR) of 2.5 (95% CI: 1.4-4.4). Similarly, under ATP III criteria, the age group 50-59 showed higher odds (AOR=2.1, 95% CI: 1.0-4.1) for metabolic syndrome. Additionally, employment status was associated with a lower risk, as employed individuals exhibited decreased odds of MetS (AOR=0.4, 95% CI: 0.2-0.9) based on both criteria.

Furthermore, lifestyle factors such as smoking and chewing tobacco did not show adjusted significant association. Similarly, we did not find association between insufficient fruits and vegetable intake, physical activity and MetS. Notably, BMI categories were strong indicators of MetS, with participants classified as obese exhibiting the highest odds, particularly under IDF criteria (AOR=6.2, 95% CI: 2.5-15.1). These findings highlight the multifactorial nature of metabolic syndrome and underscore the importance of addressing both demographic and lifestyle factors in its prevention and management.

Table 3: Univariate and multivariate analyses showing the factors associated with metabolic syndrome (n=347)

<i>Variables</i>	<i>ATP III Criteria</i>		<i>IDF Criteria</i>	
	COR (95% CI)	AOR (95% CI)	COR (95% CI)	AOR (95% CI)
<i>Age groups</i>				
30-39	Ref	Ref	Ref	Ref
40-49	1.2 (0.7-1.9)	1.1 (0.6-1.9)	2.3 (1.4-3.7)	2.5 (1.4-4.4)
50-59	1.7 (0.9-3.0)	2.1 (1.0-4.1)	1.1 (0.6-2.1)	1.8 (0.9-3.9)
≥60	1.8 (0.6-5.2)	1.8 (0.5-6.4)	0.9 (0.3-2.8)	0.9 (0.2-4.2)
<i>Gender</i>				
Male	Ref	Ref	Ref	Ref
Female	1.5 (1.0-2.3)	1.1 (0.5-2.6)	2.8 (1.8-4.4)	1.7 (0.7-4.2)
<i>Education</i>				
Primary	Ref	Ref	Ref	Ref
SSC	0.7 (0.3-1.3)	1.0 (0.5-2.1)	0.6 (0.3-1.1)	0.7 (0.3-1.6)
HSC & above	0.6 (0.3-1.13)	1.2 (0.5-2.7)	0.5 (0.2-0.9)	1.2 (0.5-2.9)
<i>Employment</i>				
Unemployed	Ref	Ref	Ref	Ref
Employed	0.5 (0.3-0.8)	0.4 (0.2-0.9)	0.3 (0.2-0.5)	0.4 (0.2-0.9)
<i>Marital status</i>				
Unmarried	Ref	Ref	Ref	Ref
Married	1.2 (0.5-2.6)	1.2 (0.5-3.1)	1.1 (0.5-2.6)	0.9 (0.4-2.4)
<i>Smoking</i>				
Never	Ref	Ref	Ref	Ref
Current	0.9 (0.5-1.7)	1.8 (0.9-3.9)	0.4 (0.2-0.8)	1.1 (0.5-2.6)
Past	1.3 (0.4-4.6)	1.3 (0.3-5.5)	0.5 (0.1-1.9)	1.0 (0.2-5.3)
<i>Chewing tobacco</i>				
Never	Ref	Ref	Ref	Ref
Current/past	1.8 (0.9-3.4)	1.7 (0.8 (3.6)	1.5 (0.8-2.8)	1.4 (0.6-3.1)
<i>Variables</i>				
	COR (95% CI)	AOR (95% CI)	COR (95% CI)	AOR (95% CI)
<i>Insufficient fruits and vegetable</i>				
Yes	Ref	Ref	Ref	Ref
No	0.8 (0.5-1.3)	0.7 (0.4-1.1)	1.2 (0.7-1.9)	0.9 (0.5-1.5)
<i>Physical activity</i>				
Inactive	Ref	Ref	Ref	Ref
Active	1.0 (0.6-1.5)	0.9 (0.6-1.5)	1.2 (0.7-1.8)	1.0 (0.6-1.7)
<i>BMI categories</i>				
Normal/Under weight	Ref	Ref	Ref	Ref
Over weight	1.8 (1.2-2.9)	2.0 (1.2-3.8)	3.2 (1.9-5.1)	3.1 (1.8-5.1)
Obese	3.9 (1.8-8.5)	4.0 (1.8-8.9)	8.1 (3.5-19.0)	6.2 (2.5-15.1)

COR: Crude Odds Ratio; AOR: Adjusted Odds Ratio for each other; ATP III: Adult Treatment Panel III; IDF: International Diabetes Federation; Ref: Reference category, Values in bold represent statistically significant results (p<0.05)

Discussion

The findings of this cross-sectional study conducted in urban Dhaka yield crucial insights into the prevalence of individuals with metabolic syndrome (MetS) and its association with socio-demographic and lifestyle factors.

The influence of age on MetS was noteworthy, particularly in the 40-49 age group under IDF criteria and 50-59 age group under ATP III criteria, which demonstrated a significantly higher odds ratio. This aligns with previous research highlighting an increased risk of MetS with advancing age.¹⁵ Though gender was significantly associated in the bivariate model under IDF criteria, it became nonsignificant when adjusted in the multivariate model for other cofounders. Many studies often report a higher prevalence of MetS in women¹⁶ but our study did not exhibit such a trend.

Employment status played a crucial role in influencing the risk of metabolic syndrome. Employed individuals exhibited decreased odds for both ATP III and IDF criteria. This finding aligns with existing literature that has often linked unemployment or job insecurity to adverse health outcomes.^{17,18} The workplace environment, when supportive and conducive to health, can serve as a facilitator for healthy lifestyle choices and overall well-being. In contrast, our study did not find any significant association between education levels, marital status, and MetS—a deviation from findings in other studies.^{19,20} This unexpected result prompts further investigation into the complex interplay of socio-demographic factors in the context of metabolic health.

The study also delved into lifestyle factors, revealing intriguing associations with MetS. We did not find any significant association between smoking, chewing tobacco and MetS which is inconsistent with the previous literature.²¹ It prompts further investigation into the potential confounding effects of other variables and the complex interplay between tobacco habits and metabolic health. Additionally, insufficient fruits and vegetable intake and physical activity levels did not exhibit an overall significant association with MetS which also contradicts with other studies²²⁻²⁴ highlighting the complexity of the relationship between food habit, exercise and metabolic health.

However, BMI categories emerged as robust indicators of metabolic syndrome, consistently showing significant associations under both criteria. Participants classified as obese exhibited the highest odds, particularly under IDF criteria, aligning cohesively with findings from parallel studies.²⁵ These findings emphasize the importance of central obesity and overall adiposity in the development of MetS. The study contributes valuable evidence supporting the inclusion of waist-hip ratio and BMI assessments in routine screenings for MetS risk.

In conclusion, this cross-sectional study in the urban Mirpur area identified a notably elevated occurrence of metabolic syndrome, with rates of 43.2% and 42.9% according to ATP III and IDF criteria, respectively, showcasing substantial disparities across diverse demographic and lifestyle segments. Noteworthy patterns included higher odds among the 40-49 and 50-59 age groups and employed individuals. Furthermore, the study heightened risk associated with being overweight or obese. These findings lay the foundation for a comprehensive exploration of the intricate interplay between demographic characteristics, lifestyle factors, and metabolic syndrome in the urban setting.

This urban Dhaka cross-sectional study sheds light on significant factors associated with metabolic syndrome. The increased risk observed among middle-aged and older individuals which underscores the need for age sensitive health programs. Employment status emerges as a crucial determinant, emphasizing the potential impact of supportive workplace environments on metabolic health. While associations with smoking, chewing tobacco, insufficient fruit and vegetable intake, and physical activity levels were inconclusive, further research is needed to unravel their complex interplay with metabolic health. Importantly, the consistent correlations between BMI categories and MetS advocate for their incorporation into routine screenings, reinforcing their significance in public health strategies aimed at preventing and managing MetS in urban populations. These insights pave the way for targeted interventions to address the multifaceted determinants of metabolic syndrome in urban contexts.

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References

1. Boutayeb A. The double burden of communicable and non-communicable diseases in developing countries. Vol. 100, Transactions of the Royal Society of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene. 2006. p. 191–9.
2. International Diabetes Federation. The IDF consensus worldwide definition of the Metabolic Syndrome. 2006.
3. Aryal N, Wasti SP. The prevalence of metabolic syndrome in South Asia: A systematic review. Vol. 36, International Journal of Diabetes in Developing Countries. Springer India; 2016. p. 255–62.
4. Institute for Health Metrics and Evaluation. GBD Compare [THE LANCET [Internet]. 2019 [cited 2022 Nov 13]. Available from: <https://www.thelancet.com/lancet/visualisations/gbd-compare>
5. icddr b. icddr,b. 2023 [cited 2023 Nov 15]. Non-communicable diseases. Available from: <https://www.icddr.org/news-and-events/press-corner/media-resources/non-communicable-diseases>
6. Executive Summary of the Third Report of the National Cholesterol Education Program (NCEP) Expert Panel on Detection, Evaluation, and Treatment of High Blood Cholesterol in Adults (Adult Treatment Panel III). JAMA. 2001;285(19):2486–97.
7. Grundy SM, Cleeman JI, Daniels SR, Donato KA, Eckel RH, Franklin BA, et al. Diagnosis and management of the metabolic syndrome: An American Heart Association/National Heart, Lung, and Blood Institute scientific statement. Circulation 2005;112:2735–52.
8. Alberti KGMM, Zimmet P, Shaw J, George : K, Alberti MM, Aschner P, et al. Metabolic syndrome-a new world-wide definition. A Consensus Statement from the International Diabetes Federation. Vol. 23, Diabetic Medicine. 2006.
9. Alberti KGMM, Eckel RH, Grundy SM, Zimmet PZ, Cleeman JI, Donato KA, et al. Harmonizing the metabolic syndrome: A joint interim statement of the international diabetes federation task force on epidemiology and prevention; National heart, lung, and blood institute; American heart association; World heart federation; International atherosclerosis society; And international association for the study of obesity. Circulation. 2009; 120:1640–5.
10. Kaur J. A comprehensive review on metabolic syndrome. Vol. 2014, Cardiology Research and Practice. Hindawi Limited; 2014.
11. Martín-Timón I. Type 2 diabetes and cardiovascular disease: Have all risk factors the same strength? World J Diabetes. 2014;5(4):444.
12. Adhikari B, Pokharel S, Mishra SR. Shrinking Urban Greenspace and the Rise in Non-communicable Diseases in South Asia: An Urgent Need for an Advocacy. Frontiers in Sustainable Cities. 2019 Nov 22;1.
13. Monower M, Flora MS, Akhter A, Akter A, Choudhury SR. Framingham Risk Assessment of Coronary Heart Diseases in Selected Area of Dhaka City: A Cross-Sectional Study. JNHFB. 2018;7:12–7.
14. Huang PL. A comprehensive definition for metabolic syndrome. DMM Disease Models and Mechanisms. 2009 May;2(5–6):231–7.
15. Gupta R Das, Tamanna RJ, Akonde M, Biswas T, Chakraborty PA, Hossain MB. Prevalence and associated factors of metabolic syndrome among Bangladeshi adults: Evidence from a nation-wide survey. Diabetes Epidemiology and Management. 2022 Jan 1;5.
16. Chowdhury MZI, Anik AM, Farhana Z, Bristi PD, Abu Al Mamun BM, Uddin MJ, et al. Prevalence of metabolic syndrome in Bangladesh: A systematic review and meta-analysis of the studies. BMC Public Health. 2018 Mar 2;18(1).
17. Green F. Health effects of job insecurity. IZA World of Labor [Internet]. 2020; Available from: <https://wol.iza.org/articles/health-effects-of-job-insecurity/long>
18. Griep Y, Kinnunen U, Nätti J, De Cuyper N, Mauno S, Mäkikangas A, et al. The effects of unemployment and perceived job insecurity: a comparison of their association with psychological and somatic complaints, self-rated health and life satisfaction. Int Arch Occup Environ Health. 2016 Jan 1;89(1):147–62.
19. Silventoinen K, Pankow J, Jousilahti P, Hu G, Toumihlehto J. Educational inequalities in the metabolic syndrome and coronary heart disease among middle-aged men and women. Int J Epidemiol. 2005 Apr;34(2):327–34.
20. Troxel WM, Matthews KA, Gallo LC, Lewis ;, Kuller H. Marital Quality and Occurrence of the Metabolic Syndrome in Women [Internet]. Available from: <http://archinte.jamanetwork.com/>
21. Sun K, Liu J, Ning G. Active Smoking and Risk of Metabolic Syndrome: A Meta-Analysis of Prospective Studies. PLoS One. 2012 Oct 17;7(10).
22. Lee M, Lim M, Kim J. Fruit and vegetable consumption and the metabolic syndrome: A systematic review and dose-response meta-analysis. British Journal of Nutrition. Cambridge University Press; 2019;122:723–33.
23. Zając-Gawlak I, Pelclová J, Groffik D, Přidalová M, Nawrat-Szołtysik A, Kroemeke A, et al. Does physical activity lower the risk for metabolic syndrome: a longitudinal study of physically active older women. BMC Geriatr. 2021 Dec 1;21(1).
24. Lee J, Kim Y, Jeon JY. Association between physical activity and the prevalence of metabolic syndrome: from the Korean National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey, 1999–2012. Springerplus. 2016 Dec 1;5(1).
25. Liu W, Lin R, Liu A, Du L, Chen Q. Prevalence and association between obesity and metabolic syndrome among Chinese elementary school children: A school-based survey. BMC Public Health. 2010;10.